

INVESTIGATION ON THE EFFECTS OF TIME MANAGEMENT STYLES ON STUDENTS STUDYING SPORTS SCIENCES AND ACADEMIC SUCCESS

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Abstract:

The research was conducted to determine the effect of time management styles and academic achievement of time management on the students in sports sciences. The universe of the research is 950 students studying at Physical Education and Sports High School, Physical Education and Sports Training, Sports Management and Coaching Education Department of Mehmet Akif Ersoy University. The sample group consists of 317 students selected by random sample method from these students. Survey data were obtained by questionnaire method. The clearness, coverage and reliability of the questionnaire developed for the purpose have been provided. The Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient of the questionnaire was 0.74. The questionnaires were applied to sample group interviewing one to one by random sampling method. A total of 317 individuals, 99 female and 218 male, responded to the questionnaire. Chi-Square (X^2) test procedures to determine the differences between the variables and the frequency (%), crosstabs as statistical process were applied. In determining the differences between the variables, it was accepted as 0.05 confidence interval. According to the obtained data, it was determined that the participants were not enough to plan the work and time they would usually do and we can say that they spend their time with tasks that are not worth their benefit, and that planning their time has a positive effect on academic success. There is no statistically significant remark difference in gender variability and time management and planning ($P > 0,05$).

Keywords: time management, student, academic achievement

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1. Introduction

Scientists seem to be describing the concept of time by discussing it in various ways according to the same points of view.

Time is a non-renewable, irreplaceable, irreversible, constantly moving and disappearing resource), apart from sources such as money, materials, machinery and human capabilities (Eilon, 1993). Time is the unique source which is non-renewable, non-storable, unstoppable, and non-substitutable in any ways. Time is all the time we spend in our lives, there is a maximum time limit that every human being can use, and although it never seems to end, it is never infinite (Fidan, 2011).

According to Drucker, time is a "scarce", "unique" and "non-flexible" resource. According to Mc. Kenzie, "extremely kind". Laken says "time is life and is the main source" (Genç, 2007).

Martin Scoot says that time is an invaluable resource, that he rushes away with a certain rhythm, and that time cannot be reversed, that the time cannot be bought more, the only thing to be done is that the time owed is best assessed and it is the least understood and the worst used resource among the resources owned (Scoot, 1997).

The desire to succeed in people's work has created the need to use their time more effectively and efficiently and revealed the concept of time management. The effectiveness of individuals in their work in every field depends on their good use of their time.

According to various definitions in various writings, time management is the use of all resources efficiently in order to perform the tasks that need to be done, within a time frame in which it's starting and ending are defined and determined (Ardahan, 2003). Another definition is the effort of the efficient use the time, which is an important resource to achieve the goals, effectively (Karaođlan and Yaman, 2009).

According to Lakein (1973), time management, according to the determined purpose, is to determine the needs, to prepare, to rank and schedule the tasks to be done according to the priority and the setting of the time after list is made (Francis-Smythe and Robertson, 1999).

Time management is a technique to improve personal performance, which is considered important in order to achieve the determined goals, to supervise the work done and to raise one's own endeavor (Gürbüz and Aydın, 2012).

The needs must be priority determined in order to manage time effectively and efficiently, establishing the targets necessary to meet these needs, determining the work to be done and planning the time according to these priorities are necessary (Lakein, 1973; Akt: Smythe and Robertson, 1999; Uđur, 2000). And it is necessary to be prepared by taking precautions against the problems that may occur in this process (Gözel, 2010).

The effective use of people's time does not depend solely on how they will use and plan their time. Individuals are faced with a number of problems being derived from themselves and from the outside when planning to use their time effectively and efficiently. We can define these problems standing on the use of time effectively and efficiently as "*things having the time consumed*"

We can evaluate 'things having the time consumed being derived from both the self and the outside.

The things having the time consumed that originate from the self are "*indecisiveness, unplannedness, no priority in the work to be done, no to say no to disrupt the work, postponement of the work to be done and not to put things in a certain order*".

The things having the time consumed arising from external factors; unexpected visitors, ineffective use of communication tools, inappropriate working environment.

All of these are leading causes of influencing the plans and practices that individuals will use to manage their time and to use their time effectively and efficiently. Therefore, these reasons also affect the success of the individuals.

It is important for individuals to plan their time effectively and efficiently so that they can succeed in their work. Effective and efficient use of time can vary according to the work each individual does. The rapid increase of the amount of vocational and educational knowledge and skills anticipated from the individual today is to reveal the need for good use of time to be successful in every field.

This research was done with purpose of determining the effects of time management styles, the things having the time consumed, time managements and the students in the field of sports sciences on the academic achievements.

2. Material and Method

The survey is a survey in the survey surveillance model. The surveillance model is a research approach aimed at describing the past or present as it exists. The event that is the subject of the research and the individual or object tries to describe as if it is within its own conditions. There is no effort to change or influence them in any way (Karasar, 2007).

The universe of the research is 950 students studying at Mehmet Akif Ersoy University Sports High School of Physical Education, Physical Education and Sports Training, Sports Management and Coaching Education Departments. The sample group consisted of 317 students selected by random sample method from these students.

Survey data were obtained by questionnaire method. (Bahçecik and Ark, 2004) prepared a questionnaire using the "*time management scale for nurse managers and factors affecting time management*" scale. The clarity, coverage and reliability of the developed questionnaire are provided. The Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient of the questionnaire was 0.74. There are a number of methods for calculating the reliability of the developing surveys for a research. The most widely used model is the Alpha Model and can be defined as (Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient) (Lorlu, 2015). The Cronbach's Alpha number is a value between 0 and 1; it is the average of a weighted standard change which is found by the ratio of the sum of the variances of the "k" items in the scales to the general variance (Özdamar, 2002). The Alpha coefficient is also a measure of the internal consistency of the items on the questionnaire. The survey includes a total of 20 questions, 3 for demographic characteristics, 9 for time management forms, 7 for the things having the time consumed, and 1 for academic achievement. Responses to

question proposals are of the "likert" type, always, intermittently (sometimes), and never.

The questionnaires were applied to sample group interviewing one to one by random sampling method. A total of 317 individuals, 99 female and 218 male, answered the questionnaire.

Chi-Square (X^2) test procedures in determining the differences between the variables and the frequency (%), Crosstabs as statistical process were applied to the data that was got, it was accepted as 0.05 confidence interval.

3. Results

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of participants

Variables	N (Distribution)	% (Distribution)	
Gender distribution	Male	218	68,8
	Female	99	31,2
	Total	317	100,0
Class distribution	1.class	158	49,8
	2.class	83	26,2
	3.class	51	16,1
	4.class	25	7,9
	Total	317	100,0
The department they study for	Physical education teaching	73	23,0
	Coaching education	103	32,5
	Sports management	141	44,5
	Total	317	100,0

Table 2: Participants' time management forms distribution

Variables		Always	Sometimes	Never	Total	X^2/P
1. I begin the day planning my time	Male	65	123	30	218	4,165 0,125
		29,8%	56,4%	13,8%	100,0%	
	Female	30	63	6	99	
		30,3%	63,6%	6,1%	100,0%	
	Total	95	186	36	317	
2. I do the list of what I have to do	Male	36	111	71	218	1,484 0,476
		16,5%	50,9%	32,6%	100,0%	
	Female	21	44	34	99	
		21,2%	44,4%	34,3%	100,0%	
	Total	57	155	105	317	
3. I do the program of what I have to do at school	Male	76	102	40	218	1,657 0,437
		34,9%	46,8%	18,3%	100,0%	
	Female	30	54	15	99	
		30,3%	54,5%	15,2%	100,0%	
	Total	106	156	55	317	
	Total	33,4%	49,2%	17,4%	100,0%	

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4. I plan before what I do one week later	Male	72	117	29	218		
		33,0%	53,7%	13,3%	100,0%		
	Female	35	56	8	99		1,804
		35,4%	56,6%	8,1%	100,0%		0,406
Total	107	173	37	317			
5. I set myself dates to finish my studies	Male	73	102	43	218		
		33,5%	46,8%	19,7%	100,0%		
	Female	39	52	8	99		6,871
		39,4%	52,5%	8,1%	100,0%		0,032*
Total	112	154	51	317			
6. I mark important dates for me on a calendar	Male	75	67	76	218		
		34,4%	30,7%	34,9%	100,0%		
	Female	44	32	23	99		4,832
		44,4%	32,3%	23,2%	100,0%		0,089
Total	119	99	99	317			
7. If I have more than one job, I put them in order of importance.	Male	107	93	18	218		
		49,1%	42,7%	8,3%	100,0%		
	Female	52	38	9	99		,518
		52,5%	38,4%	9,1%	100,0%		0,772
Total	159	131	27	317			
8. I take notes of purposes on a daybook which I set out daily	Male	33	86	99	218		
		15,1%	39,4%	45,4%	100,0%		
	Female	15	37	47	99		,138
		15,2%	37,4%	47,5%	100,0%		0,933
Total	48	123	146	317			
9. At the end of a day, I evaluate how I used the time that day.	Male	56	103	59	218		
		25,7%	47,2%	27,1%	100,0%		
	Female	25	51	23	99		,647
		25,3%	51,5%	23,2%	100,0%		0,724
Total	81	154	82	317			
Total							
P<0,05*							

Table 3: Participants' time spending formation distribution

Variables		Always	Sometimes	Never	Total	X ² /P	
1. A long day passed. I have some days I do nothing	Male	55	136	27	218		
		25,2%	62,4%	12,4%	100,0%		
	Female	13	76	10	99		7,055
		13,1%	76,8%	10,1%	100,0%		0,029*
Total	68	212	37	317			
2. On a school day I share more time to my personal care than my classes	Male	89	92	37	218		
		40,8%	42,2%	17,0%	100,0%		
	Female	37	52	10	99		3,970
		37,4%	52,5%	10,1%	100,0%		0,137

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	Total	126 39,7%	144 45,4%	47 14,8%	317 100,0%	
3. I spend long time on telephone, internet etc.	Male	56 25,7%	103 47,2%	59 27,1%	218 100,0%	
	Female	25 25,3%	51 51,5%	23 23,2%	99 100,0%	,647
	Total	81 25,6%	154 48,6%	82 25,9%	317 100,0%	0,724
4. I do things obstructing my studies so that I cannot say no to my friends.	Male	47 21,6%	130 59,6%	41 18,8%	218 100,0%	
	Female	12 12,1%	64 64,6%	23 23,2%	99 100,0%	4,199
	Total	59 18,6%	194 61,2%	64 20,2%	317 100,0%	0,123
5. I have days on which I study late at nights.	Male	53 24,3%	112 51,4%	53 24,3%	218 100,0%	
	Female	24 24,2%	55 55,6%	20 20,2%	99 100,0%	,725
	Total	77 24,3%	167 52,7%	73 23,0%	317 100,0%	0,696
6. I have habit of postponing work I have responsibility for.	Male	38 17,4%	108 49,5%	72 33,0%	218 100,0%	
	Female	13 13,1%	56 56,6%	30 30,3%	99 100,0%	1,589
	Total	51 16,1%	164 51,7%	102 32,2%	317 100,0%	0,452
7. On an imp. course assignment, I have days I study one night before the last day of delivery.	Male	83 38,1%	108 49,5%	27 12,4%	218 100,0%	
	Female	35 35,4%	49 49,5%	15 15,2%	99 100,0%	,529
	Total	118 37,2%	157 49,5%	42 13,2%	317 100,0%	0,768

P<0,05*

Table 4: Participants' answer to proposition "I study for my classes daily by planning my time even though not an examination" and academic achievement distribution

Variables	Always	Sometimes	Never	Total	X ² /P
2.01-2.50	12	43	38	93	
	12,9%	46,2%	40,9%	100,0%	
2.51-3.00	14	53	33	100	
	14,0%	53,0%	33,0%	100,0%	
3.01-3.50	13	46	30	89	12,135 0,059*
	14,6%	51,7%	33,7%	100,0%	
3.51-4.00	12	16	7	35	
	34,3%	45,7%	20,0%	100,0%	
Total	51	158	108	317	
	16,1%	49,8%	34,1%	100,0%	

P<0,05*

4. Discussion and Conclusion

A total of 317 individuals participated in the survey. Of these, 68.8% were male and 31.2% were female, 49.8% in the first class, 26.2% in the second class, 16.1% in the third class, 7.9% in the fourth class. 23% in physical education teaching, 32.5% in coaching education and 44.5% were studying in sports management (Table 1).

4.1 When time management and planning forms of participants are examined

When we look at the answers given by the participants for the question "*I start the day by planning my time*", it is seen that 58.7% 'sometimes', 30% 'always' and 11.4% responded 'never'. When we look at the answers given according to gender variable, it is seen that the comparative statistical analysis value [$X^2 = 4,165$, $P = 0,125$] (Table 2.1). This value was not statistically significant at the level of significance of 0.05 either ($P > 0.05$). When we examine the table in detail, we can say that most of the participants start the day by planning their time occasionally.

When we examine the responses of the participants to the preposition of "*I do list of things I have to do*", It can be seen that 48.9% 'sometimes', 33.1% 'never', and 18% answered 'always'. It is seen that the comparative statistical analysis value of answers given according to gender variable is [$X^2 = 1,484$, $P = 0,476$] (Table 2.2). This value is not statistically significant either ($P > 0.05$). As a result of all the data obtained, we can say that the participants have occasionally done the list of the tasks they have to do.

When we look at the answers given by the participants in total for the question preposition "*I do the program of the things I have to do at school*", it is seen that 49.2% of them 'sometimes', 33.4% 'always' 7.4% say never. The comparative statistical analysis value of responses given according to gender variable was found as [$X^2 = 1,657$, $P = 0,437$] (Table 2.3). This value is not statistically significant either ($P > 0.05$). As a result of this data, we can say that the most of the participants sometimes do the program of the work they have to do in school.

When we look at the answers given by participants in the question "*I plan before what I do one week later*", it is seen that 54.6% of them 'occasionally', 33.8% 'always', 11.7% say 'never'. In a comparative statistical analysis of the inter-variable responses, [$X^2 = 1,804$, $P = 0,406$] was found (Table 2.4). This value is not statistically significant either ($P > 0,05$). According to the collected data, we can say that the majority of participants sometimes do the plan of the work to be done one week later.

When we scrutinise the answers in total to the question preposition "*I set myself the date to finish my studies*", it is seen that 48,6% of them 'sometimes', 35,3% 'always', 16,1% say never. In the comparative statistical analysis of responses given according to gender variable, it is seen that [$X^2 = 6,871$, $P = 0,032$] (Table 2.5). These values are significant at the level of significance of 0.05 too ($P < 0.05$). In other words, there is a difference of opinion in the answers given according to the genders. According to this data, we can say that the participants mostly set themselves a date to finish their studies. In the gender variable, female participants set a date in more time to finish their work compared to men.

When we scrutinise the participants' responses in total to the question preposition "*I mark important dates for me on a calendar*", it is seen that 37.5% of them 'always', 31.2% 'sometimes', and 31.2% mark options of 'never' the comparative analysis value of answers given according to gender variable was found as [$X^2 = 4,832, P = 0,089$] (Table 2.6). This value is not statistically significant either ($P > 0,05$). According to this data, we can say that the most of the participants mark important dates for them on a calendar.

When we scutinise the participants' responses in total to the question "*If I have more than one job, I put them in order of importance.*" It is seen that 50.2% of them 'always', 41.3% 'sometimes', and 8.5% mark answers of 'never'. It is seen that the comparative statistical analysis value of responses given according to gender variable is [$X^2 =, 518, P = 0, 772$] (Table 2.7). This value is not statistically significant either ($P > 0.05$). As a result of this data obtained, we can say that the most of the participants rank according to the importance of order when there is more than one work to be done.

When we look at the responses in total to the preposition "*I take notes of puposes on an agenda for which I set out daily*", it is seen that 46.1% of them 'never', 38.8% 'sometimes and 15.1% answered 'always'. In comparative statistical analysis of responses given according to gender, [$X^2 =, 138, P =, 933$] was found (Table 2. 8) .This value is not statistically significant eithers ($P > 0.05$). According to this, we can say that the most of the participants do not notes of purposes which they set up.

When we scrutinise the responses of participants in total to the question "*At the end of a day, I evaluate how I use time that day?*", it is seen that 48.6% of them 'sometimes', 25.9% 'never' and 25.6% answered 'always' (Question 9). It is seen that the comparative statistical analysis value of responses given according to gender variable is [$X^2 =, 647, P = 0,724$] (Table 2.9). This value is not statistically significant either ($P > 0$, As a result of the collected data, we can say that the most off the participants query how they evaluate that time at the end of a day.

According to all these values obtained, we can say that the most of the participants do time management and planning occasionally. There is no significant difference in answers given according to gender variable. In Similar researches that have been conducted, (İşcan, 2008, Erdem, Piriñçi and Dikmetaş 2005, Durmaz, Hüseyinli and Güçlü, 2016) the findings which are that there is no significant difference between women and men in terms of time management skills overlap with the research findings.

4.2 When we scrutinise the questions of time spending forms of the participants

When we look at the answers in total given by the participants for the question "*A long day passed, I have the days I do nothing*", it is seen that 66.9% of them 'sometimes', 21.5% 'always' and 11.7% answered 'never'. In a comparative statistical analysis of responses given by gender variable, [$X^2 = 7,055, P = 0,029$] was found (Table 3.1). This value was statistically significant at the level of significance of 0.05 too ($P < 0.05$). In other words, there are differences of opinion in responses to this question the participants answered according to gender. We can say that most of the participants do

not plan their time according to this obtained data. In the gender variable, we can say that women question themselves by saying that I did nothing at the end of a day according to men.

When we scrutinise the responses of participants in total to the question "*I share more time for my personal care than my lessons on a school day*", it is seen that 45.4% of them were 'sometimes', 39.7% 'always' and 14.7% answered 'never'. In comparative statistical analysis of responses given according to gender [$X^2 = 3.970$, $P = 0.137$] was found (Table 3.2). This value is not statistically significant either ($P > 0.05$). According to the obtained data, we can say that the most of the participants occasionally share more time for their personal care than their lessons and the answer 'always' follows this.

When we look at the answers given by the participants for the question "*I spend long time on phone, internet and devices like that*", it is seen that 46.6% of them 'sometimes', 25.9% never' and 25.6% mark options of 'always'. In comparative statistical analysis of responses given according to gender variable, [$X^2 = 647$, $P = 0,724$] was found (Table 3. 3). This value is not statistically significant either ($P > 0.05$). According to the data obtained, we can say that the most of the participants occasionally spend long time on phone, internet and devices like that. (Değirmenci, 1994; Kibar et al., 2014; Tektaş ve Tektaş, 2010) In their studies, the opinion of that the most important factors that make students lose and spend time are television, radio and internet overlap with our research finding.

When we scrutinise the responses of the participants in total regarding the preposition "*I do things that prevent my studies because I cannot say to my friends*", it is seen that 61.2% of them 'sometimes', 20.2% 'never' and 16.2% answered 'always'. It is seen that the comparative statistical analysis value of answers given according to gender is [$X^2 = 4,199$, $P = 0,123$] (Table 3.4). This value is not statistically significant either ($P > 0.05$). According to the result of this data, we can say that the most of the participants occasionally do things that prevent their studies because they cannot say to their friends. (Kibar et al., 2014) In the researches they have done, the result of which students postponed their studies because they cannot say "no" to their friends overlaps with our research findings. (Atkinson, 1997) specifies that the most effective way to time management implementations is to be able to say 'no' and those who do it will be successful.

When we scrutinise the participants' responses in total to the question "*I have the days on which I study late at nights*", it is seen that 52.7% of them gave 'sometimes, 23.4% 'always', and 23% gave the response of 'never'. In the comparative statistical analysis of responses given according to gender variable, [$X^2 = 725$, $P = 0,696$] was found (Table 3.5). This value is not statistically significant either ($P > 0.05$). According to the data obtained, we can say that the majority of the participants occasionally study late at nights.

When we look at the responses of participants in totally to the question preposition "*I have a habit of postponing the work in my responsibilities*", it is seen that 51.7% of them 'sometimes', 32.2% 'never' and 16.1% pointed out the options of 'always'. The comparative statistical analysis value of responses given according to gender variable

[$X^2 = 1,589$, $P = 0.452$] was found (Table 3. 6). This value is not statistically significant either ($P > 0.05$). As a result of this data, we can say that the majority of the participants occasionally postpone the work in their responsibilities. (Joseph, 1994) In his studies, he states that postponing work is one of the major time management traps and a habit that will constrain from important works, demolish one's career, disrupt his happiness and prevent his success in every field.

When we scrutinise the responses of the participants in total to the question "*On an important course assignment, I have days I study one night before the last day of delivery*", it is seen that 49.5% of them 'sometimes' 37.2% 'always' and 13.2% said 'never'. When we look at the answers given by gender variable, it is seen that the comparative statistical analysis value is [$X^2 = 529$, $p = 0,768$] (Table 3.7). This value is not statistically significant either ($P > 0.05$). According to the data obtained, on an important course assignment we can say that the majority of the participants have the days they study one night. This case also shows that they do not have a study plan and they spend their time randomly.

In terms of the data obtained, we can say that participants spend their time mostly without making plans.

4.3 Participants' time schedules and academic achievements

When we scrutinize the answers given by the participants regarding the question "*The relationship between I study my classes daily by making time planning and the academic achievement*", the comparative statistical analysis was found as [$X^2 = 12,135$, $P = 0,059$] too (Table 4). These values shows that there is statistically significant relationship between time management and academic achievement at a level of significance of 0.05 ($P < 0.05$). In other words, the academic achievement of the students studying by scheduling time is higher than those who do not. (Macan, Shahai, Dipboye, and Philips, 1990) in their researchers found that time management practices had a positive effect on the average of academic performance and academic grade and In the investigations of (Britton and Tesser, 1991) on the academic achievements of university students and their time management, they found that students who use time well have a high academic achievement and the opinions and findings of (Alay and Koçak, 2002; Mace and Tira, 1999) in their researches which are that the students who practice time management skills better are more academically successful than those who do not overlap and support the finding of our research. Also in the field texts, positive time management behaviors have influence on the academic achievement of students (Misra and McKean, 2000; Campbell and Svenson, 1992).

As a result of all these data obtained; the most of the participants are not adequate for the work they will do and planning of their time and We can say that they spend their time with their personal care, telephone, internet, etc., in the unreal work because they cannot say no to their friends, studying unplannedly late at nights and with a habit of postponing the work they are going to do.

It is seen that that studying lesson by planning the time has a positive effect on the academic achievement.

5. Suggestions:

- The importance of the time to individuals in particular young people they have during their life must be explained in written and visual media.
- At each level of educational institutions, the education of the use of time and time schedule should be given to the benefit of the individuals.
- Individuals should be told not to let themselves out in the things having time consumed apart from their real work apart from their real work.
- Individuals should be offered the opportunities to spend their free time in a way that will benefit them.
- Public institutions and organizations should carry out studies in the place and the area they are in.

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